

Opportunities of the Business in The Field of Apiculture for The Rural and Tribal Areas People, (Maharashtra)

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Abstract

Indian villages and tribal areas are rich in natural resources but seems to be missing out on the progress. Because of many youths are migrating to cities for empowerment and livelihood. To prevent the migration of youth to cities, people in rural and tribal areas must be provided the sustainable sources of income. This paper mainly deals with how beekeeping business helps in economic development of rural and tribal areas people of Maharashtra and study is based on the secondary data. Apiculture is an example of a successful agricultural business. By becoming entrepreneurs, beekeepers can increase their earnings and social capital. Entrepreneurship development programs encourage youth in rural and tribal areas through special schemes to start agro-based small scale and rural enterprises. It promotes the development of rural and agricultural areas.

Keywords: Beekeeping (Apiculture), Agriculture, Opportunities, Honey Village Scheme (Madhache Gaon Yojana).

Introduction

Indian villages and tribal areas are rich in natural resources. There are many villages in Maharashtra which are blessed by nature. Those who have benefited from forest property. These nature-rich villages are located in the hill range area, but there is no direct income, people have to live with wild animals and live on forest materials.

Agriculture is the backbone of Indian economy. About 65 percent of India's people are directly engaged in agriculture and allied activities, and about 55 percent of the workforce is engaged in agricultural and allied activities (Press Information Bureau 2023). Approximately 55% of Maharashtra's total population are engaged in agriculture (Asian Development Bank). 85% tribal population of the state is engaged in agriculture. Of these 40 percent are farmers and 45 percent are agricultural labourers so about 80% of the tribal people in the state depend on agriculture for their livelihood (Maharashtra Tribal Division). Income from

agriculture does not provide sustenance. Also drought, water scarcity, seed scarcity, lack of modern technology, insufficient training, naturally saline land, climate change are having an adverse effect on agricultural production. As a result people in those areas are deprived from progress, so many youths migrate to cities for empowerment and livelihood.

To prevent the migration of youth to cities, people in rural and tribal areas must be provided the sustainable sources of income. There are many types of business that can be done along with farming. Such as animal husbandry, poultry, fishing, sericulture, and beekeeping.

Apiculture also known as beekeeping. Beekeeping is a low investment and skill Industry having the potential to offer direct employment to lakhs of people especially hill range area, tribal and unemployed youth and farmers. Sustainability of this industry is therefore vital to the country's economic wellbeing and development, and environmental protection

Nutrient environment required for beekeeping is available in many villages and tribal areas of Maharashtra. Beekeeping as a second source of income along with agriculture is beneficial to economically empower people. Maharashtra has traditional beekeepers whose efficiency can be enhanced by training them in modern beekeeping.

Maharashtra State Khadi and Village Industries Board

To provide an additional business for the people of the hill range areas of the state as a means of the state as a means of production and at the same time, to make use of the various resources of nature, in the year 1946, the Bombay Khadi and Village Industries Committee started the honey industry at Mahabaleshwar

Training of beneficiaries, distribution of beehives along with beehives and other materials, collecting honey, processing bottling, labelling branding and selling it, etc. are carried out through this Directorate. Also, the board has district offices at the district level and the Maharashtra State Khadi and Village Industries Board is work as an implementing mechanism to implement the proposed scheme.

Public awareness camps (meetings) are organized at the taluka level or by grouping villages in central places to promote and popularize the beekeeping industry. Workshop and seminar are organized by the field offices which will enable to gather the valuable technical suggestions / recommendations so as to build the strategy for better implementation of beekeeping activities. Workshops and seminars are organized involving beekeeping scientists, technical experts, leading beekeepers, farmers, leading beekeeping NGOs, honey exporters, beekeeping equipment manufacturers, bee colony suppliers, honey traders, other beekeeping stakeholders of the country and scientists from FSSAI and BISAG, etc.

Characteristics of the honey industry

1. A typical village industry.
2. No need for special space, buildings, electricity and water etc.
3. Complete indigenous technology.
4. It is possible that the growth of honey industry achieves from everyone
5. Supplement to agriculture and horticulture.
6. There is no need to spent large time on bee farming and their management.
7. There is no competition with any other industry
8. Great potential for employment generation.
9. Adequate utilization of wasteful natural resources.
10. Large scale employment is created in beekeeping

Advantages of honey industry

1. Production of pure honey.
2. Production of pure wax.
3. Due to pollination, there is increase in crop production.
4. Collection of pollen and bee venom.

5. Royal Jelly Collection.
6. Conservation and conservation of bees.
7. Help to maintain ecological balance.
8. Conservation of natural resources.

Madhache Gav Yojana

Beekeeping business started in Mahabaleshwar as a side business by providing a means of income to the farmers and tribal of Maharashtra state through honey collection. Apiculture Institute was established in Mahabaleshwar in the year 1954. The work of development of honey industry is continuously going on through the Directorate of Honey Industry of Maharashtra State Khadi and Village Board, and the Directorate of Honey, Mahabaleshwar has been recognized as the Nodal Agency of the State for the development of honey industry. In the changing times, the use of honey in ayurvedic treatment, medicinal cosmetics, weight loss, nutrition etc. is increasing tremendously. Bees play an important role in maintaining pollination, reproduction and biodiversity. On the same basis, the villages which have the necessary geographical conditions for the production of honey (Eg. Western Ghats, Vidarbha) the said project is proposed to be implemented in such villages.

The state of Maharashtra, with its abundance and diversity of natural resources, has a unique opportunity to become the leading state in the country in the field of honey. Considering all these aspects, it is planned to implement the scheme in a comprehensive manner and it has been approved to implement the concept of "honey village" across the state in villages where there are more opportunities for honey production. In the Cabinet meeting held on 14/02/2024, instructions have been given regarding 10% beneficiary participation and 90% government subsidy for honey boxes.

On behalf of the Government of Maharashtra, an innovative initiative 'Honey Village' has been implemented. For this, 'Manghar', Mahabaleshwar, Dist. Satara and 'Patgaon', Bhudargarh, Dist. Kolhapur, 'Madhache Gaon' initiative has been implemented on pilot basis in this two villages. **'Manghar' stated in Maharashtra is the first Honey Village of the India**

Manghar is a village at a distance of 10 km from Mahabaleshwar. Which is situated in the range of Sayadri. The main reason for choosing this project is that bees are reared in a collective manner in this village. Out of 100, 80 families of Manghar village are engaged in beekeeping business.

The honey is processed and then directly sold to the customers under the label of village's brand. The villagers are also being guided and trained to use the by-products to make soaps, shampoos, and oil to generate extra income.

Honey village 'Patgaon', Maharashtra

Patgaon is famous as "Honey Village." Patgaon is located in the heart of Kolhapur district. Nature of Konkan and Kolhapur is very beautiful which provides peace for mind and attracts travellers to visit them.

For honey production and beekeeping, Patgaon has been developed itself as a center of prosperity. With technology and training the efficiency of traditional beekeepers and their method of working has been improved. Hence, the capacity of production and the total production has increased. The people from Patgaon and surrounding villages getting together and a company has been started with the name of "Patgaon Madh Utpadak Shetkari Company." The company has provided employment to honey producers, sellers and women's as well as nearby village.

Patgaon and Manghar have achieved great success and have also received government awards for their achievement.

One of the most dominant honey producers in India is Maharashtra. According to news from Maharashtra

State Khadi and Village Industries Board, the plan of Honey Village will soon be implemented at other villages and tribal areas in the Maharashtra too.

Conclusion

With the help of such schemes for beekeeping, village-based tourism can be developed and the local economy transformed. With them the local people can get the opportunities of employment. The implementation of “Honey Village Scheme” of Maharashtra State Khadi and Village Industries has played a major role in the development of the people of Manghar and Patgaon. Similar to the development of this village, beekeeping has provided an opportunity to the people of other villages and tribal areas in Maharashtra to develop themselves and the village, economically and socially. Youth, farmers, non-farmers, uneducated people, many people can get permanent source of income from beekeeping. Because due to beekeeping, many peoples can get an opportunities to done businesses related to this apiculture.

References

1. Dr. ANANDHY A., BEULA K. (2019) A Study on Prospects and Potential of Beekeeping Entrepreneurship Development in KAMARAJ JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH
2. Esakkimuthu. M. and. Kameswari. VLV (2017), Entrepreneurial Potential of Small-scale Beekeeping in Rural India: A Case in Kanyakumari district, Tamil Nadu, Tropical Agricultural Research Vol. 28 (4): 411 – 424.
3. Saha GC (1990) Beekeeping for Rural Development, its Potentiality and Beekeeping against Poverty- Bangladesh Perspective Standing Commission of Beekeeping for Rural Development. Project Director, Beekeeping Project, BSCIC 139 (5th floor), Apimondia, p. 1-6.
4. K. Robinson. (2009). Role of Apiary in rural employment generation and ecological balance in Kanyakumari District (Tamilnadu, India). Journal of Basis of Basic and Applied Biology, 3(1 &2), pp. 62-66
5. Cristina Bianca POCOL1, Molly McDONOUGH2. (2015), Women, Apiculture and Development: Evaluating the Impact of a Beekeeping Project on Rural Women’s Livelihoods, Bulletin UASVM Horticulture 72(2) / 2015
6. Narang A. et al. (2022). Political, economic, social, technological, and Swot analysis of beekeeping as a successful enterprise in India; an overview. Journal of Applied and Natural Science, 14(1), 194-202.
7. Khan Ayesha. (May 13, 2022) India’s first ‘Honey Village’ to come up in Maharashtra’s manghar.Knocksense.com
8. www.mskvib.org
9. www.rural.tourism.gov.in
10. www.nbb.in
11. www.pib.gov.in
12. www.adb.org.asian
13. www.mahatribal.gov.in
14. www.karmactive.com